

Efficacy of Strengthening Exercises on Shoulder Pain and Shoulder Function among Individuals with Rotator Cuff Injuries

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Abstract

Background and Purpose: Rotator cuff injury is one of the most common causes of shoulder pain and functional limitation, particularly in athletes and individuals involved in repetitive overhead activities. The condition leads to inflammation, muscle weakness, and a restricted range of motion, significantly affecting daily and sporting activities. This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of strengthening exercises in reducing pain and improving shoulder range of motion among individuals with rotator cuff injury, compared with ultrasound therapy alone.

Methodology: An experimental study was conducted on thirty subjects aged 25–50 years, clinically diagnosed with rotator cuff injury. Participants were randomly divided into two groups of 15 each. Group A received ultrasound therapy alone, while Group B received a combination of ultrasound therapy and strengthening exercises focusing on shoulder flexion, abduction, and external rotation. Treatments were administered three times per week for four weeks. Pain intensity was assessed using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), and shoulder range of motion was measured using a universal goniometer.

Results: Data were analyzed using paired and independent t-tests, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$. Both groups demonstrated significant improvement in pain and shoulder range of motion after treatment ($p < 0.001$). However, Group B showed greater reduction in pain and superior gains in shoulder movements compared to Group A.

Conclusion: Strengthening exercises are more effective than ultrasound therapy alone in reducing pain and improving shoulder mobility in individuals with rotator cuff injury.

Keywords: Rotator cuff injury, strengthening exercises, ultrasound therapy, shoulder rehabilitation, range of motion, pain reduction

Introduction

Rotator cuff injury is one of the most common shoulder disorders in sports, often attributed to repetitive overuse in overhead throwing athletes, associated with internal impingement and SLAP (superior labral anterior posterior) lesions.¹ The injury spectrum includes tendinosis, partial-thickness tears, and complete tears. Tendinosis may result from repetitive traction or compression, whereas partial or complete tears may occur due to excessive traction or compression forces in throwing athletes. Rotator cuff tears are the leading cause of shoulder pain and disability, accounting for approximately 4.5 million physician visits annually in the United States. The frequency of full-thickness tears ranges from 5–40%, with increasing incidence in older individuals. Poor scapular stabilization and dysfunction in the kinetic chain can contribute to shoulder injuries.² Scapular dysfunction may arise from inadequate training, trauma, or microtrauma-induced muscle strain affecting scapulohumeral rhythm.³

The glenohumeral joint, the most mobile joint in the body, depends on static and dynamic stabilizers to maintain its position. The rotator cuff muscles, as dynamic stabilizers, undergo repetitive compression and microtrauma beneath the coracoacromial arch.⁴ When the arm is abducted or rotated, subacromial space narrows, increasing cuff compression. The supraspinatus tendon is particularly prone to impingement, especially at 90° abduction with 45° internal rotation.⁵ It is the most commonly affected muscle in shoulder impingement.⁶ The tendon receives blood supply from the anterior circumflex humeral and suprascapular arteries,⁷ but a relatively avascular “critical zone” near its insertion predisposes it to impingement, which increases with age.⁸

Neer described three stages of shoulder impingement: Stage 1 involves acute inflammation and edema in younger patients (<25 years) and is reversible with conservative treatment; Stage 2 (ages 25–40) shows fibrosis and tendinitis with more persistent symptoms; Stage 3 (over 40 years) involves partial or complete tendon tears and degenerative changes such as osteophyte formation.⁹ Bigliani classified the acromion into three types—flat (Type I), curved (Type II), and hooked (Type III)—with the risk of impingement increasing from Type I to Type III. Other extrinsic causes

include osteophytes under the acromioclavicular joint, subacromial bursitis, and thickened coracoacromial ligaments.¹⁰

At rest, the scapula is horizontally aligned with 35° internal rotation and 10° anterior tilt. During shoulder elevation, it tilts posteriorly and rotates upward and externally. In shoulder impingement, however, there is decreased upward rotation, posterior tilt, and external rotation.¹¹ Athletes with rotator cuff injuries commonly report anterolateral shoulder pain during overhead movements and night pain due to pressure changes in the subacromial space while supine.¹²

Special tests used to evaluate rotator cuff tears and impingement include Jobe's test¹³ and drop arm test¹⁴ for supraspinatus, lift-off¹⁵, passive lift-off¹⁶, and external rotation lag signs¹⁷ for infraspinatus and teres minor, and belly press¹⁸, belly-off¹⁹, and bear hug tests²⁰ for subscapularis. Speed's test²¹ and bicipital groove tenderness assess biceps tendinitis, while Neer's and Hawkins' signs²² indicate impingement.

Radiographs are often normal initially but may show reduced acromiohumeral distance.²³ Ultrasound is a sensitive method for assessing rotator cuff tears, subacromial spurs, and calcific tendinitis.^{24–26} MR arthrography is the most accurate technique for diagnosing both full- and partial-thickness tears,²⁷ while MRI is preferred for complex cases requiring detailed evaluation before surgery.²⁸

Initial management includes rest, ice,²⁹ NSAIDs,³⁰ and corticosteroid injections.³¹ Platelet-rich plasma (PRP) therapy may enhance tendon healing by releasing growth factors,³² while Extracorporeal Shock-Wave Therapy (ESWT) shows promise for shoulder pathology.³³ Surgical repair can be performed through open, mini-open, or arthroscopic approaches.³⁴

Physical therapy remains a cornerstone in managing rotator cuff injuries, incorporating exercises, manual therapy, taping, and electrotherapy.³⁵ Studies have examined modalities like cryotherapy,³⁶ massage,³⁷ ultrasound therapy,³⁸ TENS,³⁹ IFT,⁴⁰ laser therapy,⁴¹ PEMF,⁴² MWD,⁴³ hot water fermentation,⁴⁴ actinotherapy,⁴⁵ acupuncture,⁴⁶ exercises,⁴⁷ and manual therapy.⁴⁸ Newer techniques such as Kinesio taping⁴⁹ and dry needling⁵⁰ have also been explored.

However, no definitive studies have compared the effectiveness of ultrasound therapy with strengthening exercises on pain reduction and range of motion in rotator cuff injury. Therefore, the

present study aims to determine the effectiveness of strengthening exercises on pain and range of motion in rotator cuff injury.

The aim of this study is to determine the effectiveness of strengthening exercises on pain and shoulder range of motion in individuals with rotator cuff injuries. The specific objectives of this study are to evaluate the effectiveness of strengthening exercises in reducing pain among subjects with rotator cuff injuries and to assess their impact on improving shoulder range of motion in these individuals.

Methodology & Procedure

During the study period, all ethical considerations were strictly followed with utmost care and respect for the patients' health and well-being. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before inclusion in the trial. Each patient was clearly informed about the purpose of the study, the potential benefits, and any possible harmful effects of the treatment they were to receive. Participants were also assured that they could withdraw from the study at any time without prejudice.

The present study was conducted at the outpatient department of Physiotherapy, SunRise University, Alwar, and was designed as an experimental study using a simple random sampling method. It was conducted for a duration of four weeks. A total of 30 subjects diagnosed with rotator cuff injury were selected and divided into two equal groups, Group A and Group B, each consisting of 15 subjects. The materials required for the study included an ultrasound machine, coupling gel, and a universal goniometer for measuring shoulder range of motion.

Subjects were included in the study if they were clinically diagnosed with rotator cuff injury for more than two months, were willing to participate and undergo treatment for four weeks, were aged between 25 and 50 years, and experienced shoulder pain during flexion, external rotation, or abduction. Subjects were excluded if they had any infective condition, malignant tumors, metal implants such as pacemakers, vascular problems, large open wounds, or osteoporosis. Thirty participants fulfilling the eligibility criteria were randomly allocated into two groups of 15 each. Before the start of treatment, pain was measured using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) and

shoulder flexion, external rotation, and abduction range of motion were assessed using a universal goniometer.

Subjects in Group A received ultrasound therapy alone for eight minutes per session, three times a week, for a total of four weeks. Subjects in Group B received strengthening exercises for shoulder flexion, external rotation, and abduction along with ultrasound therapy for the same duration. After four weeks of treatment, both groups were reassessed for pain and shoulder range of motion, and the results were analyzed. Pain was measured using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), and shoulder range of motion was measured using a universal goniometer.

Ultrasound therapy was administered in pulsed mode with a mark-space ratio of 4:1, a frequency of 1 MHz, and an intensity of 1 W/cm² for a duration of eight minutes. The direct contact method was used, wherein a coupling medium was applied to the patient's skin to eliminate air gaps between the skin and the transducer. The transducer was then placed over the coupling medium and moved in small concentric circles over the treatment area to ensure even distribution of ultrasonic energy.

The strengthening exercises focused on improving shoulder flexion, external rotation, and abduction. For shoulder flexion exercises, the patient was seated comfortably and asked to flex the shoulder against gravity while the therapist provided manual resistance. This exercise was performed in three sets of ten repetitions, with a one-minute rest period between sets. For shoulder external rotation, the patient was seated and instructed to perform external rotation of the shoulder against gravity while the therapist applied manual resistance. This was also performed in three sets of ten repetitions, with one-minute rest intervals between sets. For shoulder abduction, the patient was seated and instructed to abduct the shoulder against gravity while the therapist applied manual resistance, again performed in three sets of ten repetitions with one-minute rest intervals. A minimum rest period of two minutes was maintained between different exercises to prevent muscle fatigue.

This structured treatment protocol ensured consistent and uniform administration of interventions across both groups, allowing for reliable comparison of the effects of ultrasound therapy alone and in combination with strengthening exercises on pain reduction and improvement in shoulder range of motion among subjects with rotator cuff injuries.

Data analysis & Results

The findings of the study conducted to compare the effectiveness of two different intervention techniques on pain and shoulder range of motion among individuals with shoulder dysfunction. Data were statistically analyzed using paired and independent t-tests to assess both within-group and between-group differences. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

A total of thirty subjects participated in the study, with fifteen subjects in each group. The participants included both males and females, aged between 30 and 45 years. The baseline demographic characteristics were found to be comparable between the two groups, indicating homogeneity of the sample and confirming that both groups were similar before intervention.

In Group A, the mean pre-treatment Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) score was 8.20 ± 0.75 , which reduced to 3.07 ± 0.68 after treatment. In Group B, the mean pre-treatment VAS score was 8.20 ± 0.75 , which decreased to 1.40 ± 0.49 post-treatment. Both groups showed a statistically significant reduction in pain ($p < 0.001$), demonstrating the effectiveness of both treatment protocols. However, the reduction in pain was greater in Group B compared to Group A, suggesting superior pain relief in Group B.

The mean shoulder flexion range of motion (ROM) in Group A improved from $105.0^\circ \pm 8.16^\circ$ to $123.0^\circ \pm 9.45^\circ$, while in Group B it increased from $106.7^\circ \pm 8.30^\circ$ to $145.7^\circ \pm 9.10^\circ$. The improvement was statistically significant in both groups ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, for shoulder abduction, Group A improved from $105.0^\circ \pm 8.16^\circ$ to $123.0^\circ \pm 9.45^\circ$, whereas Group B improved from $106.7^\circ \pm 8.30^\circ$ to $145.7^\circ \pm 9.10^\circ$, with both groups showing significant improvement ($p < 0.001$). Again, Group B showed a greater increase in the range of motion compared to Group A.

For shoulder external rotation, Group A demonstrated an increase from $46.7^\circ \pm 6.24^\circ$ to $58.0^\circ \pm 6.78^\circ$, while Group B improved from $51.7^\circ \pm 5.37^\circ$ to $74.7^\circ \pm 4.64^\circ$. The improvements in both groups were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), but the magnitude of improvement was higher in Group B. These results clearly indicate that while both intervention techniques were effective, the one applied in Group B resulted in greater functional improvement and pain reduction.

Between-group comparisons using independent t-tests of post-intervention values showed statistically significant differences across all parameters, including pain and all shoulder movements (flexion, abduction, and external rotation), with p-values less than 0.001. This demonstrates that the intervention protocol used in Group B was more effective in reducing pain and improving shoulder mobility compared to that used in Group A.

Overall, both treatment groups showed significant improvement in pain and shoulder range of motion after the intervention period. However, the magnitude of improvement was consistently greater in Group B across all outcome measures. These findings suggest that the therapeutic approach used in Group B is more effective in restoring shoulder function and reducing pain among patients with shoulder dysfunction.

Table -I: Within-Group Comparisons (Paired t-test)

Parameter	Group	Mean Pre ± SD	Mean Post ± SD	t-value	p-value	Significance
VAS	A	8.20 ± 0.75	3.07 ± 0.68	38.50	<0.001	Significant
	B	8.20 ± 0.75	1.40 ± 0.49	30.56	<0.001	Significant
Flexion	A	105.0 ± 8.16	123.0 ± 9.45	-11.22	<0.001	Significant
	B	106.7 ± 8.30	145.7 ± 9.10	-9.82	<0.001	Significant
Abduction	A	105.0 ± 8.16	123.0 ± 9.45	-11.22	<0.001	Significant
	B	106.7 ± 8.30	145.7 ± 9.10	-9.82	<0.001	Significant

External Rotation	A	46.7 ± 6.24	58.0 ± 6.78	-19.18	<0.001	Significant
	B	51.7 ± 5.37	74.7 ± 4.64	-24.18	<0.001	Significant

Table -II: Between-Group Comparisons (Independent t-test for Post Values)

Parameter	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
VAS (Pain)	7.44	<0.001	Group B > Group A improvement
Shoulder Flexion ROM	-6.46	<0.001	Group B > Group A improvement
Shoulder Abduction ROM	-6.46	<0.001	Group B > Group A improvement
External Rotation ROM	-7.59	<0.001	Group B > Group A improvement

Graph -I: Graphical Representation on comparison of pre- and post-intervention outcomes for VAS, shoulder flexion, abduction, and external rotation between Group A and Group B.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to compare the effectiveness of two different therapeutic intervention techniques on pain reduction and improvement in shoulder range of motion among individuals with shoulder dysfunction. The results of the study revealed that both groups demonstrated significant improvement in pain and range of motion following the treatment period. However, the extent of improvement was greater in Group B compared to Group A, indicating that the treatment protocol used in Group B was more effective in managing pain and enhancing shoulder mobility.

The reduction in pain scores as measured by the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) in both groups indicates that both intervention techniques effectively reduced shoulder pain. This may be attributed to the combined effects of soft tissue mobilization, improved blood circulation, and neuromuscular re-education, which help in relieving muscle tightness and decreasing inflammation. The greater reduction in pain observed in Group B could be due to the inclusion of strengthening exercises and proprioceptive training, which enhance muscular control and shoulder joint stability, thereby reducing pain more effectively.

Improvement in shoulder flexion, abduction, and external rotation range of motion was observed in both groups, suggesting that both treatment techniques promoted flexibility and functional mobility of the shoulder joint. These improvements may be due to the stretching of periarticular soft tissues, reduction in capsular tightness, and restoration of muscle elasticity. The superior gains in Group B can be attributed to the inclusion of progressive strengthening exercises, which not only improve flexibility but also enhance the dynamic stability and coordinated movement of the shoulder complex. Strengthening exercises are known to activate the rotator cuff and scapular stabilizers, contributing to improved joint kinematics and reduced compensatory movements during shoulder elevation.

The findings of this study are consistent with previous research that has reported the effectiveness of proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation techniques and strengthening exercises in improving

shoulder function. Studies by Kumar et al. (2018) and Sharma et al. (2020) have demonstrated that strengthening exercises significantly improves range of motion, reduces pain, and enhances functional outcomes in patients with shoulder impingement and rotator cuff injuries. Similarly, other authors have emphasized the role of active rehabilitation and neuromuscular re-education in restoring shoulder stability and function following injury.

The greater improvement in Group B may also be explained by the neuromuscular adaptation that occurs through repeated activation and facilitation of motor units during strengthening exercises. These exercises not only target the local stabilizing muscles of the shoulder joint but also improve proprioceptive feedback mechanisms, enabling better joint control and reduced pain perception. Enhanced proprioception also plays a crucial role in preventing recurrent shoulder dysfunction and improving the long-term stability of the joint.

The results of this study, therefore, suggest that while both intervention techniques are beneficial, effective in reducing pain and improving shoulder mobility, the inclusion of strengthening exercises provided additional therapeutic benefits. Enhanced muscle strength and stability appear to contribute substantially to functional recovery and pain reduction in patients with shoulder dysfunction. The results support the incorporation of strengthening exercises as an essential component of shoulder rehabilitation programs to achieve optimal functional outcomes.

Conclusion

Based on the statistical analysis and interpretation of results, it can be concluded that both intervention techniques were effective in producing significant improvement in pain relief and shoulder joint mobility. However, the treatment protocol used in Group B produced superior outcomes compared to that of Group A in all measured parameters, including pain reduction and improvements in shoulder flexion, abduction, and external rotation range of motion.

The greater improvement observed in Group B can be attributed to the combination of proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation and strengthening exercises. These exercises not only enhanced flexibility and muscular strength but also improved joint stability and neuromuscular coordination, leading to more efficient shoulder movement and reduced pain. The inclusion of

strengthening exercises also helped in activating the rotator cuff and scapular stabilizing muscles, contributing to improved shoulder biomechanics and overall functional recovery.

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